

Explore

Notes

Output Created		01-SEP-2024 21:55:32
Comments		
Input	Data	C:\Users\jkroa\Documents\Course Work\AntsAnalysis\ExpData.sav
	Active Dataset	DataSet1
	Filter	<none>
	Weight	<none>
	Split File	<none>
	N of Rows in Working Data File	6023
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values for dependent variables are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics are based on cases with no missing values for any dependent variable or factor used.
Syntax		EXAMINE VARIABLES=SmlArenaPerm MedArenaPerm LrgArenaPerm BY Type /PLOT BOXPLOT STEMLEAF NPLOT /COMPARE GROUPS /STATISTICS DESCRIPTIVES /CINTERVAL 95 /MISSING LISTWISE /NOTOTAL.
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:01.78
	Elapsed Time	00:00:02.06

[DataSet1] C:\Users\jkroa\Documents\Course Work\AntsAnalysis\ExpData.sav

Type

Case Processing Summary

	Type	Valid		Cases Missing		Total	
		N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
SmlArenaPerm	Beacon	3003	100.0%	0	0.0%	3003	100.0%
	Random	3003	100.0%	0	0.0%	3003	100.0%
MedArenaPerm	Beacon	3003	100.0%	0	0.0%	3003	100.0%
	Random	3003	100.0%	0	0.0%	3003	100.0%
LrgArenaPerm	Beacon	3003	100.0%	0	0.0%	3003	100.0%
	Random	3003	100.0%	0	0.0%	3003	100.0%

Descriptives

Type		Statistic	Std. Error		
SmlArenaPerm	Beacon	Mean	95.5133	.30870	
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	94.9081	
			Upper Bound	96.1186	
		5% Trimmed Mean	95.0391		
		Median	90.4000		
		Variance	286.167		
		Std. Deviation	16.91648		
		Minimum	63.38		
		Maximum	138.08		
		Range	74.70		
		Interquartile Range	29.00		
		Skewness	.477	.045	
		Kurtosis	-.977	.089	
		SmlArenaPerm	Random	Mean	105.3867
95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound			104.7814	
	Upper Bound			105.9919	
5% Trimmed Mean	105.8609				
Median	110.5000				
Variance	286.167				
Std. Deviation	16.91648				
Minimum	62.82				
Maximum	137.52				
Range	74.70				
Interquartile Range	29.00				
Skewness	-.477			.045	
Kurtosis	-.977			.089	
MedArenaPerm	Beacon			Mean	199.4533
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	198.3015	
			Upper Bound	200.6052	
		5% Trimmed Mean	198.7845		
Median	199.0400				

Descriptives

Type		Statistic	Std. Error
	Variance	1036.381	
	Std. Deviation	32.19287	
	Minimum	128.16	
	Maximum	299.94	
	Range	171.78	
	Interquartile Range	46.54	
	Skewness	.239	.045
	Kurtosis	-.440	.089
Random	Mean	225.5867	.58747
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	224.4348
		Upper Bound	226.7385
	5% Trimmed Mean	226.2555	
	Median	226.0000	
	Variance	1036.381	
	Std. Deviation	32.19287	
	Minimum	125.10	
	Maximum	296.88	
	Range	171.78	
	Interquartile Range	46.54	
	Skewness	-.239	.045
	Kurtosis	-.440	.089
LrgArenaPerm	Beacon	Mean	309.4467
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	308.0847
		Upper Bound	310.8087
	5% Trimmed Mean	309.0610	
	Median	308.0600	
	Variance	1448.971	
	Std. Deviation	38.06535	
	Minimum	209.80	
	Maximum	425.00	
	Range	215.20	
	Interquartile Range	54.28	
	Skewness	.149	.045
	Kurtosis	-.413	.089
	Random	Mean	360.0133
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	358.6513
		Upper Bound	361.3753
	5% Trimmed Mean	360.3990	
	Median	361.4000	
	Variance	1448.971	
	Std. Deviation	38.06535	
	Minimum	244.46	
	Maximum	459.66	

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plots

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot of SmlArenaPerm
for Type= Beacon

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot of SmlArenaPerm
for Type= Random

MedArenaPerm

Stem-and-Leaf Plots

MedArenaPerm Stem-and-Leaf Plot for
Type= Beacon

Frequency	Stem & Leaf
4.00	12 . &
38.00	13 . 23678899&
116.00	14 . 00112233445566677788889999
208.00	15 . 000001111122222333334444455555666667777788888999999
259.00	16 . 000000111111222222333333444444555555666666777777888888999999
274.00	17 . 0000000111111222222233333333444444445555555666666777777888888999999
297.00	18 . 000001111111222222233333333344444444445555555566666666777777888888999999
337.00	19 . 000000001111111122222222333333333344444444445555555556666666677777788888
8899999999	
353.00	20 . 000000001111111112222222223333333333444444444455555555566666666777777
8888888889999999	
329.00	21 . 00000000011111111222222222333333333344444444445555555566666667777778888888
99999999	
260.00	22 . 00000001111111122222223333334444445555566666677777888888999999
194.00	23 . 0000001111122222333344445555666677777888899999
130.00	24 . 0000111122233444555666777888999
92.00	25 . 0001122334455667778899
57.00	26 . 01234456678&
33.00	27 . 123345&
17.00	28 . 024&&
1.00	29 . &
4.00	Extremes (>=291)

Stem width: 10.00
Each leaf: 4 case(s)

& denotes fractional leaves.

MedArenaPerm Stem-and-Leaf Plot for
Type= Random

Frequency	Stem &	Leaf
4.00	Extremes	(=<134)
6.00	13 .	&
24.00	14 .	12489&&
47.00	15 .	01124678899&
75.00	16 .	001234556677788999
108.00	17 .	00112233444555666777888999
162.00	18 .	00011122223333444455556666777788889999
222.00	19 .	00001111222223333344444555556666677778888899999
288.00	20 .	00000011111122222333334444455555666667777788888999999
347.00	21 .	0000000011111122222233333344444555556666677777888
88888899999999		
348.00	22 .	000000000111111222222333333444445555566666777778888
88889999999999		
320.00	23 .	0000000000111112222223333334444455555666667777788888888
99999999		
291.00	24 .	000000000111111222222333334444455555666667777888888999999
273.00	25 .	0000000011111222223333344444555556666677777888888999999
239.00	26 .	00000011111222223333344444555556666677777888889999
159.00	27 .	00001112222333344444555566667778899
75.00	28 .	0011223344556678&
15.00	29 .	012&

Stem width: 10.00
Each leaf: 4 case(s)

& denotes fractional leaves.

Normal Q-Q Plots

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plots

LrgArenaPerm

Stem-and-Leaf Plots

LrgArenaPerm Stem-and-Leaf Plot for
Type= Beacon

Frequency	Stem & Leaf
1.00	20 . &
9.00	21 . &&
18.00	22 . 456&&
41.00	23 . 01234556789
89.00	24 . 0001122334455667778899
135.00	25 . 000011122233445556666777888999
174.00	26 . 001111222233334444455556666777888999
235.00	27 . 0000011111112222233333334444455556666777788888999999
281.00	28 . 0000000111111112222223333333444445555566666667777778888888999999
285.00	29 . 0000011111112222223333334444444555556666666777777888888999999
288.00	30 . 00000111111122222223333333344444444555556666666777778888889999999
291.00	31 . 00000011111112222222233333334444444555566667777778888889999999
270.00	32 . 0000000111111222222333334444444555566666777777788888999999
224.00	33 . 000000112222233333344444455555666677777888899999
189.00	34 . 00001111222223333344444455556667778889999
164.00	35 . 00000111122223333344445556667778889999
121.00	36 . 000001122333344555667788899
78.00	37 . 001123334455567889
56.00	38 . 00112334456899&
33.00	39 . 014689&&
14.00	40 . 14&&
4.00	41 . &
3.00	Extremes (>=420)

Stem width: 10.00

Each leaf: 4 case(s)

& denotes fractional leaves.

LrgArenaPerm Stem-and-Leaf Plot for
Type= Random

Frequency Stem & Leaf

3.00 Extremes (<=250)
5.00 25 . &
15.00 26 . 7&&&
35.00 27 . 0346789&
53.00 28 . 023455567889&
80.00 29 . 00123334455566678899
125.00 30 . 000111223333444555666778889999
168.00 31 . 00001111122233344455566667777888899999
195.00 32 . 000011112223333444444555566666677777888999999
223.00 33 . 000011111222233333444444455556666667778889999999
270.00 34 . 00000011111111222222333344444455556666677777888889999999
289.00 35 . 000000000111111222222333334444445555666666777777888889999999
285.00 36 . 00000000111111222222333334444445555666666777777888889999999
290.00 37 . 0000000111111222222233333344444555566666677777888889999999
278.00 38 . 000000001111112222223333344444555566666777778888889999999
227.00 39 . 0000000111112222333344445555666667777788888999999
172.00 40 . 00011112223333344445556666778888999
134.00 41 . 000111222333344456667888999
89.00 42 . 00012223345667888999
39.00 43 . 12344578&
19.00 44 . 34&&
9.00 45 . &&

Stem width: 10.00
Each leaf: 4 case(s)

& denotes fractional leaves.

Normal Q-Q Plots

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plots

